

Brown planthopper biotypes in India

R. Velusamy, postdoctoral fellow, IRRI;
S. Chelliah, professor of Entomology,
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University
(TNAAU), Coimbatore 641003; E. A.
Heinrichs, entomologist and head, and
F. Medrano, assistant scientist,
Entomology Department, IRRI

The differential response of rice varieties to the brown planthopper (BPH) in international screening tests indicated that the BPH population on the Indian subcontinent is not the same as natural populations in other Asian countries. Further studies were conducted to compare the response of rice varieties to BPH populations from southern India and BPH populations maintained at IRRI in the Philippines.

Adult BPH were collected from fields at TNAU, Coimbatore; Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai; Agricultural College, Madurai; and Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry, to study the biotype variation. Populations were cultured separately on TN1 plants. Pregerminated seeds of rice varieties ARC6650, ARC10550, ASD7, ASD11, Babawee, IET5741, IET6315, Mudgo, Rathu Heenati, Sinna Sivappu, T7, V. P. Samba, and the susceptible check TN1 were sown in standard seedboxes. Ten days after sowing, seedlings were infested with second- and third-instar nymphs and seedboxes were covered with fiberglass mesh cages. Damage was scored using the 0-9

Reaction^a of rice accessions to BPH populations collected from different regions.

Accession	Gene for resistance	Damage rating ^b			
		Population from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry	Population in the Philippines		
			Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Mudgo	<i>Bph</i> 1	9 d	1	9	1
ASD7	<i>bph</i> 2	9 d	1	3	9
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph</i> 3	3 c	1	3	1
Babawee	<i>bph</i> 4	3 c	1	3	1
Sinna Sivappu	Not known	1 a	1	3	1
ARC6650	Not known	1 a	1	3	1
ARC10550	Not known	1 a	9	9	9
ASD11	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
IET5741	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
IET6315	Not known	2 b	9	9	9
T7	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
V. P. Samba	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
TN1	No resistance	9 d	9	9	9

^aBased on the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice 0-9 scale. ^bMean of three replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale when 90% of the TN1 seedlings died.

Known differential varieties and selected rice accessions reacted similarly to BPH from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry, but Mudgo and ASD7 rices, carrying *Bph* 1 and *bph* 2 resistance genes, were susceptible to BPH populations from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry, while Rathu Heenati (*Bph* 3) and Babawee (*bph* 4) were resistant (see table). ARC6650, ARC10550, IET5741, IET6315, T7, ASD11, Sinna Sivappu, and V. P. Samba showed consistently resistant reactions to BPH from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry. ARC6650, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, and Sinna Sivappu are resistant to BPH bio-

type 1, biotype 2, and biotype 3 in the Philippines but IET5741, IET6315, T7, ASD11, and V. P. Samba are highly susceptible.

Thus the *Bph* 1 and *bph* 2 genes did not confer resistance to the Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry BPH populations; however, *Bph* 3 and *bph* 4 genes conferred resistance to BPH populations occurring in the Philippines and in South India. ARC6650 and Sinna Sivappu also possessed a high level of resistance to the Philippine and the south Indian BPH populations. Those differential varietal reactions indicate that the BPH population in Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry is different from the Southeast Asian population. □

Occurrence of *Porthesia xanthorrhoea* Koller on summer rice

S. U. Kittur, R. K. Agrawal, and A. K. Badaya, Zonal Agricultural-Rice Research Station, Raipur 492 012, India

The hairy caterpillar *Porthesia xanthorrhoea* Koller was first recorded at Raipur on summer rice in Apr 1983. Estimated moth population was 189/ha, with 1:1 sex ratio. Moths were active until Jun. Because no plant damage, except for egg masses on middorsal leaf surfaces, was apparent in the field, laboratory studies were initiated to determine feeding behavior and life cycle.

Oval egg masses measuring 1.2 cm are covered with pale brownish yellow hair, and appear similar to those of *Scirpophaga incertulas* Wlk. An average of 65 larvae hatched from each egg mass after a 6-d incubation.

Newly hatched caterpillars fed on tender leaf sheaths and on cut stems. About 23% first-instar and 43% seventh-instar larvae died in the laboratory. Disease caused seventh-instar death. Pre-oviposition was 2 d, oviposition was 1-2 d, and total life cycle was 47 d.

In the laboratory, larvae were fed whole stems, cut stem pieces, or preflowering, milky, and dough stage spikelets, or a

combination of those. Larvae did not feed on entire stems or milk and dough stage spikelets. But they readily fed on cut stems by tunneling up to 2 to 6 mm. They also fed on preflowering spikelets. They fed on tender leaves (leaving only the midrib) and sometimes on mature leaves. The newly hatched larvae, up to the third instar, fed gregariously on cut stems and central leaf margin, while sixth- and seventh-instar caterpillars devoured the entire top portion of stems.

Larvae fed on the stylet, stigma of the ovary, and anther lobes, but not on the filament. The palea of preflowering spikelets were cut from the middle but the

lemma was not eaten. Up to 50% of the top and 37% of the middle of preflowering spikelets were eaten and only 3.2% of preflowering spikelets were eaten from

the lateral side. An average 62% of preflowering spikelets were entirely eaten and 38% were partly eaten. The larvae fed on an average 24.8 spikelets/d during

various instars. During the sixth to eighth instar as many as 257 preflowering spikelets were eaten, which indicates the magnitude of grain loss. □

Controlling armyworm with synthetic pyrethroids and conventional insecticides

V. K. R. Sathyanandam, M. S. Venugopal, and A. A. Kareem, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625 104, India

For the first time, a severe outbreak of rice armyworm *Spodoptera mauritia* Boisd. occurred in IR20 nurseries in Oct 1983 at the Agricultural College Farm, Madurai. An average 400 to 420 third- and fourth-instar larvae per square meter was recorded. We evaluated three synthetic pyrethroids and four conventional insecticides for control. Insecticides were applied with a knapsack sprayer on 15-d-old nurseries in the evening. Treatments were in three replications. Living and dead larvae in a 1-m² area were counted 24 h after spraying and percent mortality was calculated (see table).

Evaluation of three synthetic pyrethroids and four conventional insecticides for control of rice armyworm larvae, Madurai, India.

Insecticide	Application rate (g ai/ha)	Larval mortality (%) ^a
FMC54800	12.5	100 a
FMC54800	25	100 a
FMC54800	50	100 a
FMC65318	15	100 a
FMC65318	30	100 a
FMC65318	45	100 a
Cypermethrin (Ripcord 10 EC)	50	100 a
Chlorpyrifos (Coroban 20 EC)	200	100 a
Endosulfan (Endocel 35 EC)	350	91.6 b
Phosalone (Zolone 35 EC)	350	84.9 c
Heptachlor 20 EC	500	84.1 c
Check		

^a Calculated 24h after insecticide treatment. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

FMC54800, FMC65318, cypermethrin, and chlorpyrifos were the most effective chemicals. □

Effect of insecticide application on rice growth

K. Raman, research scholar, Entomology Research Institute, Loyola College, Madras 600034; and S. Uthamasamy, associate professor, Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

Brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is the most serious rice pest in many Asian countries. We studied plant growth and biochemical changes in rice plants after foliar insecticide application.

Two 10-day-old TN1 seedlings were transplanted in 12-cm clay pots and sprayed with insecticides 20, 30, and 40 d after planting under pest-free conditions. There were 12 treatments (see table) and 3 replications. Control plants were sprayed with water. Fifteen days after the last spraying, the number of tillers and leaves and plant height in each treatment were recorded. Nutrient changes caused by insecticide application were determined by sampling 20 cm of leaf sheath and stem above the soil. Samples were dried and analyzed for total N, P, K, Ca, and Mg.

Foliar application of fenthion, methyl

Plant hosts of rice caseworm

J. P. Bandong, research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, IRRI

Twelve rice field weeds were compared to

Effect of foliar application of insecticide on TN1 plant growth, Aduthurai, India.^a

Treatment ^b	Mean numbers		Plant ht (cm)
	Tillers	Leaves	
Fenthion	8.0 a	29.0 a	72.7 a
Methyl parathion	10.0 a	30.7 a	75.7 a
Quinalphos	7.7 b	26.3 b	75.0 a
Phosphamidon	7.3 bc	25.7 bc	75.0 a
Carbosulfan	7.3 bc	24.7 c	73.7 a
BPMC	7.0 c	23.7 cd	72.3 a
Methamidophos	7.0 c	22.3 d	70.3 a
Fenvalerate	7.7 b	25.7 b	73.3 a
Permethrin	9.0 a	24.7 c	71.7 a
Cypermethrin	8.0 b	28.3 ab	74.7 a
Deltamethrin	9.0 a	29.0 a	76.0 a
Untreated check	6.7 c	20.3 b	72.3 a

^aData are means of three replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^bThe first seven are insecticides applied at 0.04%. The next four are pyrethroids applied at 0.002%.

parathion, permethrin, and deltamethrin increased tillering (see table), as did application of quinalphos, fenvalerate, cypermethrin, phosphamidon, and carbosulfan. BPMC and methamidophos did not affect tillering. Plant height was not affected by insecticide application; neither was nutrient content. Results suggest that lush growth after insecticide application might attract immigrating BPH □

rice as hosts of rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (see table). Rice caseworm eggs from a greenhouse colony were placed in cages around potted vegetative-stage plants immersed in water. Developing larvae were forced to feed on one plant species in this no-choice trial.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.